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Updated EOVS specification sheets

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Executive Summary

In response to identified gaps in the consistency and effectiveness of the existing Essential Ocean Variable (EOV) framework, the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) Biology & Ecosystems Expert Panel (BioEco Panel) undertook a systematic process to update the GOOS BioEco EOV specification sheets. This process was led and steered by the Panel Science Officer as part of the BioEcoOcean project. Through this process, a restructuring of the EOV template was carried out with the aim of improving the clarity, utility, and alignment of specification sheets across the GOOS expert panels as well as with external global reporting systems such as the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS).

This report documents the process and outcomes of updating the GOOS BioEco EOV specification sheets (Fig. 1).

A revised specification sheet template was developed through a series of online workshops supported by the BioEcoOcean project that included consultation with the other GOOS expert panels (Biogeochemistry and Physics and Climate). A key enhancement of the EOV specification sheets was the new addition of a Data Management section, offering practical guidance on contributing data and metadata to the global observing system.

To support the implementation of the new template, the BioEcoOcean project developed a *Guide to complete the EOV specification sheets* (D2.1) and supported the GOOS BioEco Panel Science Officer in convening a series of online workshops to begin drafting updated sheets. Drafts were reviewed by the BioEcoOcean consortium, with refinements discussed during an in-person workshop held in Sopot, Poland, from February 3 to 6, 2025.

Key outcomes of the update process include:

- New step-by-step guidance on how to contribute metadata and data to the global system.
- Development of first draft specification sheets for two pilot EOVs: Microbe biomass and diversity and Benthic invertebrate abundance and distribution.
- Separation of previously grouped EOVs into distinct specification sheets for Sea turtles, Marine mammals, and Seabirds.
- Completion of a revised Ocean Sound EOV specification sheet, supported by a full implementation plan developed with the support of the Partnership for Observation of the Global Ocean (POGO).

The updated BioEco EOV specification sheets are available online at: www.goosocean.org/eov

Graphical Abstract

Figure 1. Graphical abstract of the process to update the BioEco EOVS specification sheets

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
BGC	Biogeochemistry
BioEco	Biology and Ecosystems
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variable
ECV	Essential Climate Variable
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
EVs	Essential variables
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
GEO BON	Group of Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IO PAN	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences
MBON	Marine Biodiversity Observation Network
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System
OCG	Observations Coordination Group
ODIS	Ocean Data and Information System
POGO	Partnership for Observation of the Global Ocean
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UU	Uppsala University

1. Introduction

1.1 The Need for a globally coordinated ocean observing system

The ocean is central to life on Earth—it regulates climate, supports biodiversity, and provides vital ecosystem services such as food, energy, and coastal protection. Yet despite its global importance, our understanding of the ocean—particularly its biological and ecosystem dimensions—remains limited and fragmented (Muller-Karger et al., 2024). Unlike physical and chemical ocean observations, which are routinely observed through globally coordinated systems, biology and ecosystems (BioEco) observations are still largely conducted at local or regional scales, using varied methodologies and standards.

A globally coordinated ocean observing system is essential for generating the consistent, long-term, and comparable data required to track biodiversity trends, assess ecosystem health, and monitor progress toward international targets such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the Global Biodiversity Framework (Miloslavich et al., 2024; Muller-Karger et al., 2024; Satterthwaite et al., 2021). Such coordination enables alignment across initiatives, reduces duplication, fills critical gaps, and supports the production of robust indicators that can inform policy and decision-making at all levels—from local resource management to international climate strategies.

Key initiatives such as the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) are building the foundations for this global coordination. GOOS, established by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, plays a leading role in aligning ocean observing efforts through its adoption of the Framework for Ocean Observing (Lindstrom et al., 2012). This framework introduced a systems-design approach aimed at developing an integrated, sustainable, and fit-for-purpose global ocean observing system, with its implementation overseen by several structures of GOOS, including the three disciplinary expert panels on: (1) Physics & Climate, (2) Biogeochemistry, and (3) Biology & Ecosystems.

At the heart of this framework lies the concept of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)—a focused set of ocean measurements that are both scientifically valuable and feasible to observe globally (Fig 2). For biological and ecosystem observations, EOVs include variables such as plankton biomass and diversity, fish abundance and distribution, and seagrass or coral cover and composition (Miloslavich et al., 2018). The EOVS concept helps streamline efforts, providing a common language and shared priorities that enable coordination across regions, institutions, and disciplines. It also allows the observing community to concentrate resources where they are most needed, while improving data comparability and usability.

Importantly, EOVs are not only scientific tools—they are designed to support societal goals. By providing a basis for robust indicators and evidence-based assessments, EOVs help inform

conservation planning, marine spatial management, environmental reporting, and policy development. In doing so, they contribute to a shift away from fragmented, project-specific monitoring toward a coherent, global system of sustained biological and ecosystem observation.

The continued development and operationalisation of BioEco EOVS—through GOOS and in collaboration with partner networks such as GEO BON’s Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON) and OBIS—is essential for addressing persistent data gaps and achieving the level of integration required to support sustainable ocean management. In this way, EOVS are not simply technical elements of a monitoring framework; they are enablers of global alignment, strategic focus, and shared impact. Anchoring biological and ecosystem observation within the EOVS framework is a key step toward building the coordinated systems needed to safeguard ocean life and support human well-being.

Figure 2. GOOS Essential Ocean Variables. Colour coding: physics EOVS in dark blue, BGC EOVS in orange, BioEco EOVS in green, cross-disciplinary EOVS in light blue.

1.2 Integration with other Global Observation Frameworks

Connections between GOOS EOVS and other Essential Variables (EVs) were recognised from their inception, but the EV landscape has since expanded significantly. To ensure Earth system coherence, EOVS are now explicitly aligned with other EV frameworks, particularly the Essential Climate Variables (ECVs), led by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) (Bojinski et al., 2014) and the Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs), led by the Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON) (Pereira et al., 2013). GOOS serves as the ocean component of these broader global frameworks.

These framework alignments are not merely conceptual. ECVs support climate policy under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), while EBVs link to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), with GOOS ensuring ongoing compatibility for global assessments. Among the 55 ECVs identified by GCOS, 19 are ocean-related, overlapping with eleven physics and five biogeochemistry EOVS. For ocean biological ECVs, they are typically constructed by combining multiple BioEco EOVS (e.g. the plankton ECV encompasses the phytoplankton and zooplankton EOVS). Similarly, EBVs use BioEco EOVS as core building blocks—integrating data on species abundance or habitat data—enabling broader biodiversity monitoring (Bax et al., 2019; Muller-Karger et al., 2018). Collaborative efforts, like the GOOS BioEco Panel’s partnership with GEO BON’s MBON, are central to harmonizing observations across these frameworks. Such collaborations improve interoperability, reduce duplication of effort, and strengthen the collective impact of global ocean observation systems.

1.3 What are EOVS?

EOVS are key physical, chemical, and biological measurements that provide insight into ocean conditions and trends. They help us:

- Track climate change,
- Forecast weather-related events,
- Monitor the health of marine ecosystems at local to global scales.

Examples of EOVS include sea surface temperature, nutrient levels, and seagrass cover and composition.

To be considered “essential,” a variable must meet two criteria:

1. **Impact** – It provides valuable information for science, management, or policy.
2. **Feasibility** – It can be reliably and practically measured across time and space.

The EOVS framework includes 12 EOVS for biodiversity (Fig 2), measuring marine biodiversity such as microbes, phytoplankton, mangroves, seagrass, seabirds and marine mammals, etc. (Miloslavich et al., 2018). The framework also includes cross-cutting EOVS focused on ocean stressors, such as ocean sound. Through the EOVS framework, GOOS enables systematic and continuous observations that can have multiple applications.

Together with partners, such as the OBIS, the MBON, and many scientific communities around the globe, GOOS works to strengthen the collection of these key observations to support nations in advancing ocean understanding and achieving sustainable ocean management.

Each EOVS has a specification sheet that outlines its significance, offers guidance on measurement methods, and explains how to contribute and manage the resulting data effectively.

1.4 The EOVS specification sheet update

GOOS provides strategic guidance for designing ocean monitoring systems by identifying EOVS and addressing gaps in data collection. However, a 2020 review revealed that the EOVS framework did not fully meet the evolving needs of scientists and decision-makers. In response, GOOS proposed forming a dedicated task team to enhance the EOVS system, ensuring it can better support both global and regional decision-making while keeping pace with technological and scientific advances.

At the 8th GOOS Steering Committee meeting in 2020, the formation of this EOVS task team was discussed. The team's mandate included reviewing current coordination mechanisms across the three GOOS expert panels—Biogeochemistry, Physics and Climate, and Biology & Ecosystems—and harmonising guidance through a comprehensive review of the EOVS specification sheets.

At the time, each expert panel followed different processes for selecting, reviewing, and updating EOVS, using varied templates and timelines. These inconsistencies weakened the coherence and authority of GOOS guidance on observing system design. Further complexity arose from overlapping requirements with other global reporting frameworks, such as GCOS ECVs and the GEO BON EBVs. Key challenges included delays in revision cycles due to dependency on GCOS ECV reviews, incompatible templates, and the absence of a unified review framework.

Addressing these issues required coordinated action. A new specification sheet template was developed to align with both GOOS and external reporting requirements, including those from GCOS. However, updating the EOVS using this new template proved challenging. It became clear that further clarification was needed regarding the purpose of the specification sheets and their intended audience.

The BioEcoOcean project developed a “Guide to complete the EOVS specification sheets” (see BioEcoOcean Deliverable 2.1) to assist EOVS leaders in completing and updating their specification sheets. Along with the development of the Guide, BioEcoOcean also supported a process for restructuring and simplifying the EOVS specification sheet template. This report outlines the process for the creation of this new simplified template and the update of the BioEco EOVS specification sheets.

2. Improving the specification sheet template

2.1 Rationale for updating the template

Each EOVS is accompanied by a detailed specification sheet that outlines why a specific measurement is essential, defines its components, describes the ocean processes it helps capture, and provides guidance on the spatial and temporal scales required for observation. These observing requirements help ensure that data collection aligns with GOOS’s mission to deliver useful, policy-relevant information across its key focus areas: climate, weather forecasts and warnings, and ocean health.

The specification sheets also serve as a communication tool for a range of audiences:

- **For policy and decision-makers**, the sheets intend to show how EOVSs align with community needs and policy priorities, helping guide investments in observing systems and infrastructure.
- **For scientists**, they aim to offer practical guidance on observing and studying ocean processes by breaking them into measurable components (sub-variables, supporting variables, and derived products), along with their observing requirements.
- **For people collecting observations**, the sheets include information on sensors, technologies, observing approaches, and links to relevant standards, best practices, and data systems.

The specification sheets also include additional information on relevant observing networks and communities of practice, key references, as well as data repositories and products.

However, despite this broad intended use, it became clear that the template's structure and language were too technical and not well-suited to the diverse needs of these audiences. The specification sheets struggled to communicate effectively across user groups and lacked clarity in purpose and usability.

Recognising these limitations of the EOVS specification sheets, the BioEcoOcean project partnered with the GOOS BioEco Panel to undertake a revision and restructuring of the

specification sheet template. The aim was to make the language appropriate for the intended user, clarify the target audiences, and improve the overall structure so the specification sheets could better support their role as a multi-purpose communication and guidance tool before any further updates to the EOVS were made.

2.2 The process

To review and refine the structure of the EOVS specification sheet template, a series of six online workshops with GOOS BioEco Panel EOVS leaders was held in June and July 2024 with BioEcoOcean's support. Throughout these workshops, the template evolved significantly with language simplified, sections reorganised for better usability, and a new data management section introduced to guide data collectors on how to contribute their observations to the global system via OBIS.

Acknowledging the need for consistency across disciplines, the BioEcoOcean project supported additional meetings with representatives from the GOOS Physics and Biogeochemistry (BGC) panels. These discussions ensured that the revised template would meet the needs of all GOOS expert panels and led to agreement on a standardised, cross-disciplinary template. Presentations were also conducted at both the BGC and Physics panels to gather additional input about the new template structure.

2.3 A new structure for the EOVS specification sheet

The new EOVS specification sheet template is structured in such a way that each section is tailored to provide information addressing different audience requirements and takes the readers through the ocean observing value chain from observation requirements to data management and applications (Fig 3).

Figure 3. Illustration of the structure flow of the new specification sheet and the audience each section is meant to inform (pink text boxes).

The updated template for the EOVS specification sheets consists of i) Background & Justification; ii) Section 1 EOVS information, iii) Section 2 Phenomena to observe, iv) Section 3 GOOS Observing Specifications or Requirements, v) Section 4 Observing approach, platforms and technologies, vi) Section 5 Data and information management. More details are provided here:

The **Background and Justification section** provides high-level context on the importance of the EOVS, outlining the benefits of monitoring it and the potential impact of the data through contributions to global initiatives and multilateral environmental agreements. It also includes a link to the GOOS BioEco Metadata Portal, which offers information on the programs and networks collecting BioEco EOVS observations worldwide.

Section 1 EOVS information provides information on the EOVS and its three key elements:

- Sub-variables: key measurements used to estimate the EOVS. For example, counts of individuals to provide an estimate of species abundance (such as fish, mammals, seabirds, or turtles).
- Supporting variables: other measurements that provide scale or context to the sub-variables of the EOVS or in providing the derived products. For example, water turbidity to support estimations of hard coral cover.

- Derived products: outputs calculated from the EOV and sub-variables, often in combination with the supporting variables, which contribute to evaluating change in phenomena. For example, fish stock productivity can be determined from fish abundance.

Section 2 Phenomena to observe provides examples of ocean processes or phenomena the EOV helps capture, describing each phenomenon by providing their spatial and temporal extent and the resolutions needed to observe them.

Section 3 GOOS Observing Specifications or Requirements provides guidance for observing systems and data collectors outlining the recommended spatial and temporal resolution required to measure each of the sub-variables, presented across three levels; minimum, desirable, and ideal. However, the information in the table is not prescriptive; rather, it serves as a guideline. The aim is for the ocean observation community to collectively achieve these spatial and temporal resolutions through collaboration, coordination, and data sharing. By contributing standardised and comparable data, all observations, regardless of resolution, become valuable inputs toward building a comprehensive global system. Every data contribution is critical to advancing our collective understanding of the ocean.

Section 4 Observing approach, platforms and technologies provides information on observing approaches that can be used to measure the EOV, including new and old techniques as well as remote sensing techniques. This section also provides helpful links to suggested protocols and methods, serving as a resource that people undertaking monitoring can utilise.

Section 5 Data and information management focuses on data management and outlines the steps required to contribute data to the global system. Aimed primarily at data managers, it provides practical guidance, including helpful links and step-by-step instructions for submitting metadata to the BioEco Metadata Portal and contributing data to OBIS. This section is standardised across all EOVs and represents a new addition to the restructured template, filling a gap that was not addressed in the previous version.

2.4 The EOV Guide

To accompany the new template, the BioEcoOcean project developed an interactive guide (BioEcoOcean Deliverable 2.1) outlining and translating the information requested in each field of the new EOV specification sheet template. This guide was created to facilitate their update and understanding of its content. The Guide to the EOV specification sheets can be accessed here: <https://oceanexpert.org/document/36219>

3. Updating the specification sheets

3.1 Expanding the GOOS BioEco Panel

The GOOS BioEco Panel encompasses expertise for each of the BioEco EOVs (EOV leaders) and their role includes the following activities:

- Engage the broad scientific community to progress the maturity of the BioEco EOVs within their areas of expertise.
- Develop and facilitate EOV implementation plans within a global observing system, promoting best practices and data sharing, and regularly reviewing and updating the EOV specifications.
- Connect observing networks collecting observations that contribute ‘their’ EOVs to GOOS systems, including OBIS, Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS), Observations Coordination Group (OCG), etc.
- Promote consistent messaging on the justification, application, and benefits of BioEco EOVs.
- To ensure an adequate succession plan is in place during their membership term to support continuity of expertise on the Panel.

To be able to undertake these activities and ensure continuity, the GOOS BioEco Panel increased its capability by expanding the Panel to include two co-leaders per EOV. Between November and December 2024, new EOV co-leaders were appointed to the Panel.

3.2 Developing a new data management section to contribute data to the global system

Previous versions of the specification sheets lacked specific guidance for data management, despite the critical importance of ensuring clear pathways for EOV data to flow into the global system. To address this gap, a new section dedicated to data management, applicable to all EOVs, was developed to ensure data adheres to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Since the 2020 revision of the specification sheets, significant advancements have occurred with the global Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) Digital Ecosystem, including the creation of the GOOS BioEco Metadata Portal, the establishment of the Ocean Data Information System (ODIS), and the ongoing integration with OBIS. These developments necessitated mapping out the components of the digital ecosystem, delineating their connections, identifying entry points, and specifying the types of data required at each stage.

ODIS, as the most recent addition to the digital ecosystem, plays a crucial role in making data and metadata more findable. Understanding and communicating its technological connections with OBIS and the BioEco portal were essential steps in drafting the guidelines. While ongoing improvements continue to enhance connections between these systems, the guidelines were written with these advancements in mind.

The development of the data management section for the specification sheets was a collaborative effort, led by OBIS, with significant input from ODIS to ensure the guidelines accurately captured all aspects of the digital data ecosystem. A key challenge was differentiating the dual flows of information: the BioEco EOV data itself and the metadata about what we now call the "data producers" (e.g., monitoring programmes, projects, organizations, etc.). Both need to be visible in ODIS and/or OBIS. Striking a balance between these distinct flows while maintaining coherence across the document required careful thought and iterative revisions.

The process presented several challenges. Balancing the level of detail was difficult; on one hand, enough step-by-step information on how to contribute data, including links to external resources for specific details, was necessary, while on the other hand, it was important to keep the content accessible for a broad, non-technical audience. Early drafts, for instance, leaned heavily toward highly technical explanations, and significant time was dedicated to distilling this text, aiming to retain technical accuracy while simplifying the language. After this, anonymous feedback gathered from BioEcoOcean colleagues highlighted the need to further clarify the guidelines with simple, explicit steps. The section was rewritten to ensure the text provided a clear path with actionable steps without overwhelming users, as well as lists of minimally required information. The newly developed EOV Metadata Submission App, made possible through the support of the BioEcoOcean project, was instrumental in simplifying data producer metadata submission to ODIS, which otherwise is a highly technical process.

To support long-term accessibility and adaptability, the metadata and data management guidelines were moved from a static document to a GitHub repository and are now hosted online (<https://iobis.github.io/eov-data-management/>). This allows for easy updates as data guidelines evolve over time, avoiding the need to update the EOV specification sheets themselves, which now link to the resource and contain only minimal information and helpful links. This collaborative process underscored the importance of providing clear communication and iterative feedback in creating user-friendly guidelines.

3.3 Updating the specification sheets

The BioEcoOcean project supported several online workshops with each BioEco EOV to update the specification sheets, ensuring the information was both relevant and clearly

presented. In some cases, additional input was obtained from other experts, which is reflected in the list of authors on the specification sheets.

To further improve clarity and ensure the content was appropriate for ocean observing, the BioEcoOcean project consortium was invited to review the updated specification sheets. Feedback was collected through a structured survey designed to ensure comments were relevant to the content (See Appendix 1).

Figure 4. Respondents' main professional activity.

As the expertise within the BioEcoOcean project does not cover all BioEco EOVS equally, each reviewer was assigned two specification sheets: one aligned with their area of expertise and an additional sheet to ensure every EOVS received feedback. In total, 33 reviews were submitted by 17 respondents, the majority of whom were observers, followed by modellers and researchers (Fig. 4).

The BioEcoOcean project organised a joint face-to-face workshop with the GOOS BioEco Panel on February 3-7 2025, in Sopot, Poland (see agenda in Appendix 2). At this workshop, the results from the EOVS specification sheets review were discussed and areas for improvement were identified (see D2.2). Over 59% of the reviews by the project consortium found the information clear and sufficient, while fewer than 25% considered it insufficient and provided additional comments (Fig. 5).

BACKGROUND AND JUSTIFICATION

SECTION 1 - EOVS INFORMATION

SECTION 2 - PHENOMENA

SECTION 3 - OBSERVING REQUIREMENTS

SECTION 4 - OBSERVING APPROACHES

SECTION 5 - DATA MANAGEMENT

Figure 5. Feedback results from the EOVS specification sheet review by the BioEcoOcean project consortium enquiring about the clarity and completion of each section of the specification sheet. The questions of the survey can be found in Appendix 1.

Workshop participants found the specification sheets useful and provided some suggestions to the GOOS BioEco Panel for improvement including:

- Adding links to global data products that modellers can reference and use.
- Ranking observing approaches, prioritising platforms capable of collecting multiple EOVS.
- Developing a short course on the EOVS and specification sheets to support early-career researchers.

The project consortium’s feedback highlighted the importance of having clearly defined data collection methodologies, as well as the need for guidance on supplementary variables and recommended observing approaches. Discussions during the meeting emphasised the value of developing cross-EOV guidelines and including information to link (related) EOVS between specification sheets, fostering a more integrated approach to ocean observing. The workshop also highlighted the importance of aligning the EOVS specification sheets and the BioEcoOcean “Blueprint” (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Alignment between the different sections of the EOVS specification sheets and the Blueprint elements.

Based on the feedback from the project consortium, the draft specification sheets were revised by the GOOS BioEco Panel and finalised. All updated BioEco EOVS specification sheets are now available on the [GOOS website](#) for consultation and use (see Appendix 3).

This process led to several key advancements:

- Two emerging EOVS: *Microbe biomass and diversity* and *Benthic invertebrate abundance and distribution* developed draft specification sheets for the first time.
- The previously combined EOVS for *Sea turtles, Marine mammals, and Seabirds* abundance and distribution was separated, resulting in individual specification sheets for each group.
- The *Ocean Sound* EOVS finalised its full implementation plan, with support from POGO, and provided insights to the other EOVS leaders about developing implementation plans.

3.4 Next steps

The BioEco EOV specification sheets are currently being updated through an open consultation and expert workshops, aiming to strengthen coordination and standardisation in ocean biology and ecosystem observations, this work is done with support from the BioEcoOcean project. The feedback from the ocean biology and ecosystems research communities on the updated EOV specification sheets is being requested via a survey and through webinars. The process currently underway is the following:

- 1) A consultation to gather community input for the BioEco EOV specification sheets, open between 8 May and 10 August 2025 (see [here](#)).
- 2) Online workshops for each EOV with key experts will be undertaken from September to November 2025 to finalise the specification sheets.

Communication about the updated EOV specification sheets and the benefits of the BioEco EOVs as a framework for coordination for ocean biology and ecosystem observations will be undertaken through a series of webinars between July and December 2025 as a collaboration between GOOS, MBON, Air Centre and the BioEcoOcean project.

4. Conclusions

The process of updating the BioEco EOV specification sheets offered an opportunity to revise their structure, improving both clarity and practical utility. For the first time, draft specification sheets were created for the two pilot BioEco EOVs—*Microbe biomass and diversity* and *Benthic invertebrate abundance and distribution*—marking a significant advancement in their development. Further progress, including agreement on minimum metadata standards and the creation of FAIR and open data pipelines to OBIS, will enhance the overall maturity of all BioEco EOVs. This update represents an important step toward a more mature and fit-for-purpose global ocean observing system for biology and ecosystems.

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Disclosure:

AI has been used for language proofing in some parts of the document.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Survey questions for feedback on EOVS specification sheets

The purpose of the survey is to (1) evaluate the clarity of communication on EOVS through the renewed EOVS Spec Sheet template, and (2) evaluate the usefulness of the content with respect to user expectations.

[Brief explanation of EOVS provided]

Instructions:

Please read the specification sheet before providing feedback. Please read the “Guide on how to use the EOVS specification sheets” to help you navigate and understand the information provided in the template.

1. Are you a (select from the list):

- Observer
- Modeller
- Science communicator
- Data manager
- Policy/decision maker
- Other ___ what?

2. What primary information do you expect to find in an EOVS specification sheet? (free text)

3. What EOVS are you reviewing? (select from the list)

LIST OF EOVS

4. What EOVS spec sheet are you reviewing first? (choose one from list)

LIST OF EOVS

5. Does the BACKGROUND AND JUSTIFICATION section provide the needed high-level information about the importance of observing this specific EOVS?

- Yes
- No — why not?
- Can be improved — explain

6. Does SECTION 1. EOVS INFORMATION provide clear guidance on the main measurements (sub-variables) and supplementary measurements (supporting variables) needed to observe this EOVS on a global scale?

- Yes
- No --- why not?
- Other _____

7. SECTION 2. PHENOMENA TO OBSERVE includes examples of processes, events or phenomena that can be captured by the EOV measurements specified in Table 1. The table includes information to describe the spatial/temporal extent of these phenomena and the resolutions needed to observe them. (Please see the guide to understand the information provided in each field of this table). Are the example phenomena in this table relevant to the EOV and the information to describe the phenomena clear?

- Yes they are relevant to the EOV and the phenomena are clearly described
- They are relevant to the EOV but the information to describe the phenomena is not clear
- No they are not relevant to the EOV but the phenomena are described clearly
- They are neither relevant nor clearly described
- There should be other phenomena listed here instead. *If so, which ones?

Any comments?

8. SECTION 3. GOOS OBSERVING SPECIFICATIONS OR REQUIREMENTS provides guidance on creating a long-term system to observe the EOV and capture key phenomena related to the EOV. There should be one table per measurement (sub-variable) (Please see the guide to understand the information provided in each field in the table). Do the tables provide clear and sufficient guidance on each measurement and the scales needed to observe, including units of measurements where appropriate?

- Yes they provide clear and sufficient information
- No, they are not clear and more information is needed
- I don't know

Comments / Is there other essential information you think should be included here? If so, what type?

9. SECTION 4. OBSERVING APPROACHES provides information on the different observing approaches/technologies used to collect information on the EOV globally. While the list is non-exhaustive, in your view, are the approaches included in the table are the most known, feasible to implement globally and providing the most impactful information?

- Yes
- No, what approach or approaches are missing? ___

10. If you are an expert on this EOV, are there any other methods or approaches not listed that you think should be included? If so, please provide a reference.

- Yes, which one _____
- No
- I don't know

Please provide reference or any additional comments

11. Section 5 provides information on how to contribute DATA AND METADATA to GOOS. Are the instructions clear on how you would submit metadata and data to the system (ODIS and OBIS)?

- Yes
- No

Do you have any comments on the Data and Metadata section?

12. Are there any references that you think should be included in the specification sheet?

- Yes (please include the references and the relevant section in the comments)
- No

Comments

Please provide the references

Appendix 2. BioEcoOcean and GOOS BioEco Panel joint workshop agenda

Funded by
the European Union

BioEcoOcean meeting with the GOOS Biology & Ecosystems Panel of Experts

4 - 6th of February 2025

Meeting location: IOPAN, Sopot, Poland

Objectives:

- To provide the GOOS BioEcoPanel with a deeper understanding of the project and its plans to advance the uptake and implementation of BioEco EOVs
- To gather the BioEco Panel's input on the project and create the necessary connections

Agenda:

4th February 2025	
Session	Lead
9:00-9:30 (30 mins) - Overview	Lina Mtwana Nordlund
9:30-10:30 (60 mins) - Living labs overview	Living labs leads
10:30-11:00 (30 mins) - Morning tea on site	
11:00-12:20 (80 mins) - BioEcoOcean and EOv implementation	Ana Lara-Lopez, Lina Mtwana Nordlund
12:30-13:30 (60 mins) - Lunch on site	
13:30-13:45 (15 mins) - Introduction to the BluePrint	Lina Mtwana Nordlund
13:45 -15:15 (90 mins) - Blueprint workshop	Lina Mtwana Nordlund, Artur Palacz
15:15-15:45 (30 mins) - Afternoon tea on site	
15:45 -17:30 (105 mins) - Blueprint workshop cont.	Lina Mtwana Nordlund, Artur Palacz
From 18:30	Group dinner

5th February 2025

Funded by
the European Union

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Session	Lead
9:00 -10:30 (90 mins) - Data management workshop: IOC Digital Ecosystem initiative Preparing for (field) data collection: metadata + data needs Connecting to ODIS	Ward Appeltans, Elizabeth Lawrence, Pieter Provoost
10:30-11:00 (30 mins) - Morning tea on site	
11:00 - 12:30 (90 mins) - data management workshop cont.: Darwin Core: How to structure collected data and how to include multidisciplinary data in your dataset	Ward Appeltans, Elizabeth Lawrence, Pieter Provoost
12:30-13:30 (60 mins) - Lunch on site	
13:30 - 15:00 (90 mins) - data management workshop cont.: Using “computer language” for collected variables (controlled vocabulary, e.g. NERC, WoRMS) Demo: Publishing data to OBIS (IPT)	Ward Appeltans, Elizabeth Lawrence, Pieter Provoost
15:00-15:30 (30 mins) - Afternoon tea on site	
15:30 - 17:00 (90 mins) - data management workshop cont.: Demo: Accessing & using OBIS data Data products discussion	Ward Appeltans, Elizabeth Lawrence, Pieter Provoost

6th February 2025	
Session	Lead
9:00 -10:30 (90 mins) - Blueprint for end users - associated resources	Lina Mtwana Nordlund, Artur Palacz
10:30-11:00 (30 mins) - Morning tea on site	
11:00 - 12:30 (90 mins) - Way forward and wrap up	Lina Mtwana Nordlund, Artur Palacz
12:30-13:30 (60 mins) - Lunch on site, end of joint meeting.	

Appendix 3. Links to Biology and Ecosystems updated EOVS specification sheets

- [Coral cover and composition](#)
- [Seagrass cover and composition](#)
- [Macroalgae canopy cover and composition](#)
- [Mangrove cover and composition](#)
- [Microbe biomass and diversity](#)
- [Phytoplankton biomass and diversity](#)
- [Zooplankton biomass and diversity](#)
- [Benthic invertebrates abundance and distribution](#)
- [Fish abundance and distribution](#)
- [Sea turtles abundance and distribution](#)
- [Seabirds abundance and distribution](#)
- [Marine mammals abundance and distribution](#)
- [Ocean Sound](#)

Partners

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